

Contributions from Lund to WP6200-6300

(for discussion at Copenhagen-Lund meeting 1983-06-15)

1. Introduction

This is an outline of tasks which could be performed in Lund, principally by S Söderhjelm, starting with July 1983. They correspond roughly to WP6200 (algorithm development for the Primary Reference Stars solution), but could possibly include implementation of certain subroutines (WP6300).

2. Tasks

2.1. 'Old PRS experiments'

Since March 1983, small-scale simulations have been made of the PRS solution with about 20 stars, using the 'old' method, i.e. elimination of set orientations. The first task is to bring these experiments to a logical end as soon as possible, and to report on the results. Most of this is probably completed before July.

2.2. File organization

This will clarify the input/output relations and requirements for the PRS solution by describing the contents, logical and physical formats, and organization of the I/O files. This will certainly have to be revised later on, but a preliminary specification is necessary for task 2.3.

2.3. Define specific PRS routines

This should result in detailed descriptions of interfaces and algorithms (including data handling aspects) of sub-processes specific to the PRS solution, viz.:

- 2.3.1. - initialization (define stars, sets, astrometric and global parameters to be used, etc.)
- 2.3.2. - abscissa extraction (sort set results in required order)
- 2.3.3. - observation equations (form coefficients and rhs)
- 2.3.4. - system orientation (provide pseudosolution)

2.4. 'New PRS experiments'

Small-scale simulation of the 'new' method (eliminating the astrometric parameters) is needed to verify the proposed approach (process definition NDAC/LO/021) and the observability of global parameters.

3. Time schedule

The schedule below assumes 75% activity. July is counted out.

<u>Task</u>	<u>Estimated size</u>	<u>Final report</u>
old PRS experiments (finish)	0.5 man-months	1983 Aug 15
file organization	1.0 "	1983 Oct 1
new PRS experiments	3.0 "	1984 March 1
define specific PRS routines	4.0 "	1984 Sept 1

For the two major tasks, intermediate progress reports should be prepared at intervals of about six weeks.

4. Meetings

In addition to the general Copenhagen-Lund meetings, informal working meetings with 2-3 participants will be needed on a regular basis to coordinate activities. A good arrangement to start with will be for Söderhjelm and Petersen (at least) to meet in Copenhagen about every two weeks.

5. Software standards etc

We assume that the HP9000 is installed at LO in September. Manuals on the file management system (in particular) must be available for tasks 2.2 to 2.4. To familiarize ourselves with the new system and with FORTRAN 77 is obviously very important and implicit in the above tasks. To acquire a good programming style is part of the exercise.

In view of the non-standard extensions in HP FORTRAN it will also be necessary to agree on programming standards between Copenhagen and Lund. On a higher level, compatibility with VAX is required at least for certain subroutines.

6. Responsibility

Lindegren is 'task leader' for WP6200, i.e. responsible for contents and planning, while Söderhjelm takes direct responsibility for carrying out the tasks and reporting.